

Invited lecture

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE THROUGH ASIMOV'S EYES OR THE WORK OF A LIFETIME

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Abstract

This paper explores the origins and diverse implications of the terms "artificial intelligence" and "robot," highlighting their evolution and the misconceptions surrounding their use. The term "artificial intelligence" was officially coined by John McCarthy in 1956, although the concept had been explored earlier by Alan Turing and others in the field. This term encompasses a broad spectrum of technologies and applications, often misrepresented in the media as a singular entity, leading to widespread misunderstanding. Similarly, the term "robot" was popularised by Karel Čapek and initially described human-shaped machines, evolving in its application from its Slavic root meaning "labour" to signify various automated devices. The paper also delves into Isaac Asimov's significant contribution to the discourse through his literary works, mainly focusing on his portrayal of robots with "positronic brains" and the ethical and philosophical dilemmas they present. Asimov's fictional laws of robotics are discussed about real-world applications and regulatory challenges in artificial intelligence and robotics. The study underscores the disparity between Asimov's idealistic visions and the pragmatic issues of integrating AI systems into society, advocating for a nuanced understanding and responsible development of AI technologies.

Keywords

Asimov, AI, robots, ethical aspects of AI.

1 Introduction

Before analysing Asimov's oeuvre, I want to clarify a few essential points. Knowing precisely what we are talking about when we use specific terms is vital.

How long have we been dealing with things called artificial intelligence?

"Many of the early achievements could be called AI, but a complete idea of AI was formulated in 1950 by Alan Turing in his article Computing Machinery and Intelligence. Here, he introduced the concepts of the Turing test, machine learning, genetic algorithms, and reinforcement learning."(MIT BME, 2011)

After the Second World War, several researchers started researching and developing self-learning programs with decision-making capabilities. For a long time, they were called by many names until scientists working on the subject organised a two-month workshop in the summer of 1956. The subject remained many-named until John McCarthy, who later became a professor at Stanford University, named it at the Dartmouth workshop, and we still use the term today.

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As we read about it in the Artificial Intelligence Electronic Almanac:

"Perhaps the most lasting outcome of the workshop was the adoption of a new name for the field, created by McCarthy, namely artificial intelligence." (MIT BME, 2011)

As before, there were many different names for tools, what was otherwise designed for other problem areas, and the programs that work in them. Since then, we have found many interpretations of the terms and descriptions of artificial intelligence used by developers, researchers, and writers.

It is of utmost importance to note that phrases in the media about artificial intelligence, such as "Artificial intelligence already knows this." "Artificial intelligence can do it." the like creates a false image in the reader's mind. They suggest that artificial intelligence is a single thing, that we are talking about one thing when we talk about it. The consequence of this suggestion is that people unfamiliar with the subject use it in this context. Yet this interpretation is harmful, misleading, completely unscientific, and unfounded.

Yes, there has been a general term since McCarthy, but it refers to completely separate programs and the instruments they manage. Whether we are talking about a word processor or a word processor that communicates with us verbally or in writing, facial recognition software working in some hardware, or a chess machine that we play with, it is all artificial intelligence. Likewise, software that generates images or moving pictures on verbal or written request, a complex missile defence system, or machines that learn the various movements of four-legged animals or humans are all controlled by partially self-learning software and are all artificial intelligence.

But they have nothing to do with each other!

What one can do, the other can't, even if they have modules in common. The standard modules do not have identical software because they are purpose-built by experts in different research or development laboratories worldwide. One only has to think of information input. It is not the same as what and in what spectrum the input module detects and what software converts these detections into perceptions. After all, if we model humans, they perceive light in a much smaller spectrum than some animals, as we do with sound, heat, and so on. Just as the organisms on our planet perceive and react differently to different things, so do the many variations of artificial intelligence that perceive and respond differently to different things according to their programming.

There is no such thing as artificial intelligence, and it should not be discussed this way. Just as different living organisms have other purposes, different "software" such as DNA, other input and output, information processing, and execution tools, every system using artificial intelligence software is designed for different purposes.

Alongside these research and developments, automation in the industry has continued to replace humans with monotonous and exact tasks. This process continues today, with better and better robots in industry and medicine. In the 21st century, many home automation devices work in our homes, and many automats on computers and other devices do our daily robotised work.

But the robots should not be like the industrial robots we see today, but human androids!

The inventor of the word, Karel Čapek, in his drama "Rossumovi univerzální roboti", describes a human-shaped machine that can think.

"Robot" was already a familiar word in Hungary, having been one of the serf services of the Middle Ages. Although in Slavic languages, such as Russian, there is a general sense of 'work' for robots, it is also known as forced labour. ... Although Karel Čapek was the first to use the word, he did not invent it. An English-language Czech website has Čapek's recollection of all this. The short story reveals that he first wanted to call the devices "Labori", but his

brother suggested the word "robot" to describe the human-shaped machines." (HVG Kiadó Zrt., 2011)

After the drama premiere in New York in 1922, the name 'robot' began to be applied to intelligent structures in the shape of a man and later to all sorts of other mechanical devices. This led to the present-day meaning, which few people know is derived from the Slavic word for work.

Since language is a "living" evolving communication system, its words and expressions constantly change in content and meaning. The word initially meant work, but in the early Middle Ages, it already meant forced labour, work from which the person doing the work did not benefit. Work done for the landlord, done without compensation by his serfs. This quasi-slave activity is also rooted in the word robot in many languages, including Hungarian.

As Čapek understands it, a robot is a slave machine that receives no compensation for the work it does for its master.

The Isaac Asimov of the title, for example, knew it, as he described it on pages 19-20 of the Hungarian edition of *The Foundation's Edge*, where Professor Quintesetz is talking to Professor Pelorat and explaining to him about robots:

„ Quintesetz pursed his lips, leaned back in his chair (which gave slightly under the pressure), and put the tips of his fingers together. He seemed to be speculating as to just how to begin.

He said, "Do you know what a robot is?"

"A robot?" said Pelorat. "No."

Quintesetz looked in the direction of Trevize, who shook his head slowly.

"You know what a computer is, however?"

"Of course," said Trevize impatiently.

"Well then, a mobile computerised tool-"

"Is a mobile computerised tool." Trevize was still impatient. "There are endless varieties, and I don't know any generalised terms for them except mobile computerised tools."

"—that looks exactly like a human being is a robot." S.Q. completed his definition with equanimity. "The distinction of a robot is that it is humaniform."

"Why humaniform?" asked Pelorat in honest amazement.

"I'm not sure. It's a remarkably inefficient form for a tool, but I'm just repeating the legend. 'Robot' is an old word from no recognisable language, though our scholars say it bears the connotation of 'work.'"

"I can't think of any word," said Trevize sceptically, "that sounds even vaguely like 'robot' and has any connection with 'work.'"

"Nothing in Galactic, certainly," said Quintesetz, "but that's what they say."

Pelorat said, "It may have been reverse etymology. These objects were used for work, and so the word was said to mean 'work.'" „(Asimov, 1982)

As a native Russian, Isaac Judovich Ozimov, written in Cyrillic letters *Исаак Юдович Озимов*, born in 1920 in the village of Petrovichi in the Smolensk region of the Russian Federation, in the Soviet Union, obviously spoke some Russian. He was familiar with the Čapek interpretation, as the explanation points to it perfectly.

2 Artificial intelligence in Asimov's coherent stream of novels

As a famous writer, most people know Asimov as a fiction or science fiction writer and not as a scientist, so this is the primary information for his name. His works of scientific

dissemination are also very numerous, probably exceeding his works of science fiction. As an associate professor of biochemistry, he taught and chaired a department for many years until he decided to continue training more widely through his writings.

He described himself as a scientist who does science fiction when he writes about scientific dissemination. It is in no way worthy of anyone to disparage what he has written or to belittle his achievements. An author with an academic degree and a teaching 'background' who has written more than 500 books, many of which are works of scientific scholarship, is not 'just a science fiction writer'. His work is well worth reading and using in scientific works. This paper is not intended to be a literary or detailed textual analysis but merely to highlight and, rarely, justify the main points with quotations.

The present study considers Asimov's writings as part of a unified stream of thought, which many literary scholars, critics, and, of course, readers familiar with his writings, like the author of this study, consider them to be. The appearance of the short stories, short fiction, and novels is not chronological, as the short stories in *I Am a Robot* were followed by the *Foundation* trilogy. The *Space Hunter* series, the *Elijah Bayley* stories, *Pebble in the Sky*, and *Stars Like Dust* are loosely related but connected. *Prelude to Foundation*, the *Foundation Edge*, *Foundation and Earth* were completed decades after these, at the publisher's request. It is Asimov's literary genius that if you start from beginning to end in this vast reading, you become prisoners of a single stream of thought from the first to the last sentence.

Let us see what the world-famous writer and scientist wrote about artificial intelligence! His first writings coined the term "positronic brain" to describe thinking, consciousness, learning, and decision-making machines. He already uses the term robot when he imagines positronic brains in vehicles.

For 46 years, Asimov was so preoccupied with whether only humans have consciousness and the capacity for autonomous decision-making that he chose it as his central thesis, from his first science fiction writings to almost his last published novel. Had he lived in 2012, he would undoubtedly have been happy to join the signatories of the Cambridge Declaration.

What is the Cambridge Declaration? Vilmos Csányi, in his work *Ethology, Man, Society*, explains it briefly as follows:

"It has only been five years since scientists agreed that the nervous systems of man and animals are the same, with differences in size and species. In other words, the Cambridge Declaration said that animals have consciousness and that all animals think, but that these thoughts are more modest and of a different type than those of man. " (Csányi, 2017)

As the Cambridge Declaration on Consciousness, issued on 7 July 2012, states about the state of consciousness of non-human beings - non-human animals, I believe, can be named as living beings - that;

"The absence of a neocortex does not preclude an organism from experiencing affective states. Convergent evidence indicates that non-human animals have the neuroanatomical, neurochemical, and neurophysiological substrates of conscious states and the capacity to exhibit intentional behaviours. Consequently, the weight of evidence indicates that humans are not unique in possessing the neurological substrates that generate consciousness. Non-human animals, including all mammals and birds, and many other creatures, including octopuses, also possess these neurological substrates." (Low et al., 2012)

I want to add that the cleaner fish (*Labroides dimidiatus*) seems to have consciousness or some initiative to have it because it recognises itself in the mirror! (Kohda et al 2019.) It would

seem, therefore, that the Cambridge Declaration could be supplemented even after all these years in the light of scientific discoveries.

Incredibly interestingly related to this 21st-century statement is perhaps the most productive writer of the 20th century, Isaac Asimov, who returned to questions of consciousness for almost his entire creative career (nearly 50 years!).

First published in a single volume in 1964, *I, ROBOT* New York 1964 (Asimov, I. 1964.), and later published in a single volume entitled *Robot Stories* (Asimov, 1993), all his writings from 1940-1976, which contain short stories about robots and are a coherent stream of thought. However, a considerable amount of time has passed between each of them.

The message of these short stories is about artificial intelligence, robots with a positronic brain, autonomous consciousness, and the ability to think and learn, serving humans.

On the face of it, he writes stories about robots in the form of humans and other robots - vehicles, etc. - with positronic brains, self-awareness, and learning intelligence; the stories are about their masters and the interactions between them. They are exciting and entertaining writings, but those familiar with the subject will notice that they all revolve around the problem of human and artificial consciousness/intelligence. The other important topic is intuition, which is irrelevant to the present subject so that I will leave it aside.

His "Three Laws of Robotics" raises not only logical and decision problems but also ethical and psychological ones, which he has spent decades thinking about and describing and has taken to philosophical depths in his books, both for humans and robots. In the *Lucky Starr* series, he pushes the envelope on the problem of the intersection of non-human intelligence and human intelligence. At different levels, the intelligent lifeforms he imagines populate the celestial bodies of our galaxy and communicate with humans through various channels—fascinating thought experiments with philosophical and moral issues.

Giskard, whom we met in his novel *Robots of the Dawn Planet* (Asimov, 1983) and who had a conversation with R. Daneel Olivaw at the end of the novel *Robots and Empire* (Asimov, 1985) about the extension of the three laws, the introduction of the fourth law, is also a severe ethical-philosophical debate!

Robot psychology as a term also appears in the earliest collection of short stories, *I the Robot*, where the renowned robot psychologist Susan Calvin of the American Robot Ltd. is one of the main characters in many of the stories. The other protagonists are, of course, all robots who display anomalies still present in existing applications today.

In these short stories, he describes almost everything that makes us fear artificial intelligence today.

Avoiding the world of simple automatons, the author bases his writings on intelligent robots that communicate orally in increasingly clever ways, with the help of a 'positronic brain' invented in the distant future. We do not know, but it is clear that the problem of artificial intelligence and human intelligence, machine and human intelligence, and machine and human consciousness was the subject of his preoccupation, based on the assumption that robots with such capabilities would one day appear.

No one has yet produced artificial intelligence with this capability. As far as we know, current algorithms are as far from this imaginary positronic as the mind of a eukaryote is from that of a human.

One of the short stories he wrote in 1976 to celebrate the bicentennial of the United States of America, "The Bicentennial Man" (Asimov, 1983), is about a robot in the shape of a man who accidentally gains artistic powers. He uses this ability to create sought-after works of art, but his owner and descendants refuse to take the proceeds, leaving the money to his own devices.

I note that the accidental "program error" occurs twice in this series of short stories; both times, the robot develops artistic abilities. If I add to this, the ability of people in various creative fields to represent emotions, complex thoughts, or even entire stories in colours, lines, blobs, sounds, dance, etc., is not an ordinary human ability. There is a saying that very little separates the genius from the madman, and we can safely add artists to the genius. The two extremes are peculiarities in brain processes that differ from the average. The various "talents" are also distinct from the average, and because they result from the thought processes that run in our brains, they can be considered program errors.

Using this ability, the robot creates artefacts that collectors seek after and makes the robot and its owners famous. Its first owner refuses to take the proceeds from the artwork, and the money is his own. After the death of its first owner, all generations of descendants have traditionally treated the robot as a family member and an entity in its own right, as well as the memory of their ancestors, and in keeping with tradition, they have an independent income.

Throughout its long 200-year life, it continued to learn. Serving the descendants of the family that first owned it until its extinction, it explored the differences and similarities between the human brain and the positronic brain.

First, he starts wearing clothes; then, he replaces his metal body with artificial "human" body parts that look deceptively like humans. These are the kinds that humans use as prosthetics and artificial organs. After replacing all his body parts with these semi-bionic body parts, except for the positronic brain, he has only one wish: to prove that there is no difference between him and humans. Finally, the protagonist of the robot stories recognises himself as human and subsequently dies as a human.

The emotionally stirring, flat, and well-constructed writing is the first to say that there is a possibility that one day, at some point, complex software and its associated hardware might be created that is almost indistinguishable from humans. Even in the novel, it is a unique and notable exception that this robot is recognised as human and that too almost at the moment of its death.

In a series of short stories and novels written over 46 years and gradually becoming a coherent whole, he uses the term artificial intelligence only twice! The term first appears on page 58 of the Hungarian edition of "Robots of the Dawn Planet", in the last sentence of paragraph 3. Textually:

*„Viewing as he did for intuitive feel—for trend and generality—every step
In the course of human/robot interaction, it seemed to depend on dependence.
Even how a consensus of robotic rights was reached—the
gradual dropping of what Daneel would call “unnecessary distinctions”- was
a sign of the dependence. To Baley, it seemed not that the Aurorans were
growing more humane in their attitude out of a liking for the humane but that
they were denying the robotic nature of the objects to remove the
discomfort of having to recognise the fact that the human beings were
dependent upon objects of artificial intelligence.” (Asimov, 1983)*

The other time in the novel stream is on page 291 of the novel "Prelude to Foundation", textually:

*„Dors said, “It seems to be well computerised. I should think the operations
could be turned over to computers altogether. This sort of environment is made
for artificial intelligence.” (Asimov, 1988)*

These two books were originally published in 1986 and 1988, much later than the term "artificial intelligence", which, as I quoted above, was coined and adopted at the Dartmouth Workshop in 1956. It is particularly fascinating that, although he must have known it, the author avoided using the term for 30 years after its publication while he was very much involved in the subject.

In his book *The Foundation Edge* (Asimov, 1982), about the conscious planet Gaia he envisages, he describes all living and non-living parts of the earth as having some level of consciousness, from the planet's core to the last planetary gas molecule in the stratosphere. Every part of the planet knows its place and its role in its existence. These different levels of consciousness perceive each other and are capable of cooperation and collective action.

In the final volume of the series, he continues to reflect on this theme, framing all his books and short stories around this theme. At the end of *The Foundation and Earth* (Asimov, 1986), he imagines a galaxy of a community of individual consciousnesses forming a shared consciousness, a galaxy like Gaia, as a pledge of peaceful development and survival.

Asimov's work, almost half a century old, thus goes far beyond the problems of the present and the near future and even more beyond the issues of the present and the near future at the time of its writing.

He saw the dangers of the coexistence of automats and humans, the resulting conflicts, and their effects on the soul and consciousness. He did not foresee the pervasiveness of software and computers, the personal computers and their palm-worn versions, which we still call telephones by their first function, even though that is no longer the primary function for most of us.

But he was perfectly aware that there would come a point when machines would make decisions for people. He was not thinking in terms of predictive text input, spell-checkers, or a program that can write down text after dictation—although anyone who has read the *Foundation* trilogy will know that Arcadia Darell has a descriptor with such a capability—but of much deeper mechanisms that act in place of humans.

The automated airships operating on Trantor are already taking over human control, although human control can be taken back at any time. It is a bit like the rudimentary semi-autonomous vehicles, automatic emergency brakes, lane-keeping systems, ESP, ABS, and other solutions we use daily in the 21st century.

However, in the 21st century, we are increasingly aware of why Asimov's three laws of robotics should be applied in everyday life.

As a reminder:

- The First Law: A robot may not injure a human being or, through inaction, allow a human being to come to harm.
- The Second Law: A robot must obey the orders given to it by human beings except where such orders would conflict with the First Law.
- The Third Law: A robot must protect its existence as long as such protection does not conflict with the First or Second Law.

The Three Laws set out philosophical and ethical principles that a moral person should, in principle, adhere to in their own life. However, we must admit this is a romantic view of human beings. Even people who live in the most 'holy' way can occasionally make mistakes.

Of course, one could also consider that the 3 Laws of Robotics mean that individual humans and humanity have no reason to fear artificial intelligence since its basic programming precludes it from posing a threat to humans.

Related to these three is the Law mentioned above Zero, first stated by Daniel Robot Oliwaw in the book *Robots and Empire* (Asimov, 1985) in the chapter entitled *Duel*, subchapter 63:

- The Zeroth Law: A robot may not harm humanity or, by inaction, allow humanity to come to harm.

The Zero Law is a complex task with many interdependencies that go far beyond the easy and precise conditions of the first three laws. It has to consider several components that would take considerable time to count.

Asimov was driven to do this by a well-intentioned extreme idealism, somewhat divorced from reality, and a desire to continue the novel's course.

However, it would be good not to be afraid of our machines and their programs, which we create for our own benefit.

3 Asimov's principles and the reality

True, there is no artificial intelligence yet to employ, nor even robots to use them, but there are robots and software that should somehow obey the prohibition in the first turn of the first law.

Even in the absence of robots with artificial intelligence, occupational safety and health regulations are written and operated in the spirit of the first law in the design, installation, operation, and maintenance.

Obstacle detection and avoidance by cleaning robots are also designed to avoid causing injury.

For the same reason, the doors of various household vending machines, washing machines, dishwashers, and dryers cannot be opened during operation. So occupational safety and related contact and fire safety standards comply with the first law.

However, adequate protection has not been established for industrial and household cameras because the makers of the software that accompanies them have not considered the damage that could be caused if care is not taken to ensure that they are not vulnerable or to warn their users.

The fact that some computing and IOT devices may use software that takes random recordings of the user, owner, or others in the vicinity of the software being used, which are stored and transmitted, seems to me to be impermissible.

In any case, software that declares in any small print that it obtains data about its users and uses it later violates the first law of robotics.

So, protecting personal data is as much a part of the First Law as protecting life, physical safety, and health. Even mental health is immediately apparent when developers devise devious identification solutions for viewing certain content and using specific devices not to threaten the user or anyone else.

Unfortunately, we must say that we are fighting to protect personal data with little success.

The first law should also apply to addictive programs or even tools, but there is no sign of any attempt to restrict this, either by the creators of the programs or tools or by the legislators!

How many lives would have been saved if the programs of devices called 'telephones', which sometimes have the power of a computer, had been able to detect that their users were in danger in traffic situations and had stopped or warned them?

We also know of deaths where the person with a substance use disorder has played with toys for days without rest and died of addiction. We all know that members of the various age groups named with different acronyms often experience withdrawal symptoms from their usual devices, even for very short periods. I have heard many times, from many people, the clichéd phrase: "Only the machines can keep them alive!" and let's face it, there is something in it... It causes them apparent psychological damage, so it violates the first law.

Virtual reality devices and their programs can also cause severe defects in people with a substance use disorder.

We have developed several artificial intelligences that, against our will, are watching and betraying us at our expense.

Humankind has also produced several devices that automatically search, detect, identify, and destroy devices, objects, or even people, such as missile systems, the Israeli Merkava Barak tank, drone warfare devices, etc. These are capable of performing operations autonomously with significantly greater efficiency than those that would be conducted under human control alone.

Several programs have been designed and are in operation, using so-called deep fake technology (Economix. hu, 2023), which can produce images (Eisenkrammer, 2023), films (The Guardian, 2023), or even voice mimicry (economics. hu, 2023) of anyone.

Let's see where they are with the ideas of regulation. Based on a report with legal adviser and AI expert Theodore Boone, only one aspect is being examined.

"In its draft AI law - which has not yet been finalised or entered into force but appears to be in the process of being - the EU takes the view that we need to look at the risk posed by different types of AI systems and create three categories of AI systems..."

- Low-risk AI systems would be subject to minimal regulation and oversight.

- High-risk AI systems would be subject to significant oversight, transparency, and control requirements.

- Examples of AI systems that could fall into the prohibited category include real-time facial recognition AI technology used in public places. " (Balázs, 2023)

There is no mention of dangerous camel crews, AI-controlled systems capable of waging war, police, and other weapons. If there are any, they are not public principles and in no way conform to Asimovian "laws". Since the study was completed, the European Union has drafted and implemented a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules for artificial intelligence (AI legislation) and amending certain EU legislative acts, which is identical word for word to the expert opinion presented (Parliament, 2021).

The US government is not ahead of the curve on this issue. Several directives have been issued by presidential decree, such as Preserving US leadership in AI (Federal Register 2020.), Promoting the use of trusted AI in the federal government, or the Blueprint for an AI Bill of Rights (President of US, 2022) which is a legislative preparatory document that has been in the process of being developed into a usable form since 2020. It should be noted that so far, without success and military, law enforcement applications are exceptions, not included in the intended scope of this legislation. The latest US Presidential Executive Order (Executive order of President of US 2023.) on this subject, issued on 30 October 2023, is the first-ever thorough legislation, full of exceptions for military, intelligence, and criminal purposes. The planned publication of the manual on the use and rules of artificial intelligence (Executive order of President of the US 2023.) is only a draft to be published in a year, according to the Regulation. There are principles in this, too, but they do not even come close to the rigour of Asimov Law 1.

4 Conclusions

Ethical and legal principles and daily practice do not often intersect. As far as I know, there is no code of ethics with uniform criteria for software developers and mechatronic engineers.

Every manufacturer has something that considers the company's point of view and no one else's.

Asimov's Laws, in my judgment, would be ethical and suitable principles for people designing software, hardware, and robots, i.e. devices using artificial intelligence.

Artificial intelligence is a theme in the writings of Asimov's contemporary Stanislaw Lem, and it deserves special attention, but I will write about that next year.

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